

STRENGTH OF THIN SOLID POLYMER ELECTROLYTE COATINGS AND THE COATED CARBON FIBRES

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ABSTRACT

As a route to increase the efficiency of electric vehicles, weight reductions through composite building materials are constantly being introduced. To further aid this effort focus has been put on structural batteries, where the composite is multifunctional serving both as energy storing as well as load bearing unit. In an attempt to reduce the high ionic resistances solid polymer electrolytes introduces, carbon fibres have been individually coated with polymeric layers ranging from <500 nm to >3 µm in thickness. This study investigates the feasibility of using such coatings in structural applications with respect to mechanical load cycling. The coated fibres were subjected to cyclic load up to approximately 1 % strain for up to 70,000 cycles. The polymer coatings were found not to be visibly affected by the prolonged mechanical fatigue. No cracks were observed in the coatings which makes the coating technique promising for future structural battery applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Li-ion batteries are continuously being introduced as energy storing media in more and more applications. A notable example is in electric vehicles, where both pure electric vehicles as well as hybridized systems are at the moment made commercially available in large numbers [1]. A large issue with electric vehicles, however, is the relative short driving range made available with the onboard batteries. In efforts to overcome this problem two major routes can be identified: Either the batteries are made with increased specific energy, or the vehicles themselves are made lighter.

Efforts to increase the specific energy in Li-ion batteries are made in a wide range of fields from new electrode materials [2] to optimization of battery packs [3]. By making a vehicle lighter, less power will be needed to drive it, thus increasing the driving range given similar capacities of the battery packs. For this purpose an increasing use of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite materials instead of the heavier metal components as construction material has been seen [4].

For both of these broad research and development paths the battery is considered as an external device introduced into the system, with added dead weight as a consequence. To circumvent this issue, the concept of structural batteries has been suggested [5-8]. By utilizing a multifunctional material, with both load bearing and energy storing capabilities, the structural components already in the vehicle can also serve as energy source. Through such design the mass of the batteries are in theory removed as the added functionality in the structural components does not increase the mass.

A major challenge for structural battery is the fact that the solid polymers needed for the

mechanical properties dramatically reduces the conductivity of the electrolyte in the battery, as compared to the existing liquid or gel electrolytes [9]. One proposed solution is to make the electrolyte thinner, so to reduce the effect of a low conductivity [10]. This is done through coating each carbon fibre individually through an electrochemically driven polymerization process. The thickness of these coatings can be made in the range 200 nm to several micrometers. To realize this conceptualized battery an additional layer with the positive electrode is needed, which will be in intimate contact with the electropolymerized electrolyte. Due to this, the electrolyte must be absolutely pin-hole free to avoid the resulting short-circuit that will occur if the positive and negative electrodes comes into direct contact [11].

In a structural battery, mechanical loads during the battery lifetime will possibly create cracks in the carbon fibre or polymer coating thus causing battery failure. The carbon fibre and its ability to intercalate and deintercalate (cycle) lithium ions has been studied where it was found that the stiffness of the carbon fibres were largely unaffected by electrochemical cycling [12]. For the polymer coatings, however, the effect of mechanical stresses is not investigated. The aim of this study is therefore to investigate the robustness of this coating after mechanical fatigue.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Sample preparation and coating procedure

Carbon fibre (CF) bundle samples were prepared according to scheme shown in Fig. 1. Glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) tabs were glued on both ends of the sample in order to enable uniform loading of all fibers in the sample during mechanical testing. Before gluing the tabs the uncoated bundles were lightly stretched to prevent slack fibers in the bundle. Tabs were glued with an epoxy adhesive cured at room temperature for 24 hours. The final sample length between the GFRP tabs was equal to 100 mm.

Figure 1: Schematic image of a carbon fibre bundle sample

After gluing the tabs, coating of the bundles was performed. The fibres were electrically contacted and were introduced into a glove box with Argon atmosphere (<1 ppm H₂O and O₂). The electropolymerization was performed in a three-electrode electrochemical cell, with the CFs as working electrode, an additional 24k IMS65 bundle as counter electrode and a piece of lithium as reference electrode. The electrodes were submerged in a monomer solution. The monomer solution consisted of either only the monofunctional (mono) methoxy polyethylene glycol (350) monomethacrylate (SR550) (henceforth called soft), monomer or a 60:40 ratio by weight between SR550 and the difunctional (di) tetraethylene glycol dimethacrylate (SR209) (henceforth called stiff) (fig. 2), kindly supplied by Sartomer Europe. 1 M Li-triflate, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, was added in all solutions. The CF samples were polarized at 0.2 V vs. the reference electrode (REF) for 300 s according to the procedure in an earlier study [12]. The electrochemical coating was performed using a Solatron SI 1287 potentiostat controlled digitally by Corrware 3.2. After the polarization, the samples were removed from the monomer solution and washed in toluene and dried in room temperature overnight.

Figure 2: Monomer A - methoxy polyethylene glycol (350) monomethacrylate (SR550) and monomer B - ditetraethylene glycol dimethacrylate (SR209)

2.2 Mechanical load calibration

The objective of the present study was to study mechanical durability of polymer coatings. According to this objective possibly high applied mechanical strains are of interest. However, when applying high strains, the risk of fibre fracture increases, which is a different failure mechanism out of the scope of the present study. Due to statistical strength distribution of carbon fibres, the weakest fibres break at lower applied loads than the average strength of the fibres. Hence, a maximum working load was first determined below which occurrence of fibre breakage is minimal. For this reason static tensile tests were performed in an Instron 3366 testing machine with load cell capacity of 10kN. Uncoated samples were loaded in tension until complete failure in displacement control with rate of 1mm/min.

2.3 Coating characterization

The coated carbon fiber bundles were then subjected to mechanical tension-tension fatigue loading to investigate the durability of polymer coatings and to qualitatively study how it depends on the number of applied load cycles. Bundles were tested using an Instron Electropuls E3000 dynamic testing machine equipped with a load cell of 1kN capacity. The fatigue loading parameters were the following: the load ratio $R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max} = 0.1$, frequency $f = 5$ Hz. The procedure of a fatigue test is schematically shown in Fig. 3. As shown in Fig. 3 as the first step of each test a static loading-unloading cycle was performed to measure the bundle stiffness prior to fatigue loading. Cross-head speed of approximately 1 mm/min was used and the maximum load in the static step was calculated so that the strain equal to 0.35% is not exceeded. As a next step after the initial static loading-unloading step, tension-tension fatigue loading was performed according to parameters described above. The number of cycles in the fatigue test was up to 70000 cycles. After the fatigue test load cycles, the sample was once more subjected to static loading-unloading cycle as shown in Fig. 3 to measure the bundle stiffness after fatigue loading. It has to be noted that due to possible occurrence of micro-damage in the polymer coating no degradation of bundle stiffness is expected due to significantly smaller stiffness of the polymer coating compared to carbon fibres. The reduction of bundle stiffness after the fatigue test would indicate that fiber breaks have occurred during the fatigue test.

After a selected number of cycles the samples were inspected in a SEM. FEI Magellan 400 Extreme high-resolution (XHR) SEM was used for qualitative inspection of the condition of the polymer coating after a certain number of loading cycles. The tested samples were completely inserted in the sample chamber of the SEM allowing for continuation of mechanical testing after the SEM inspection.

Figure 3: Schematic lay-out of tension-tension fatigue tests of coated bundles

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical load calibration

A representative load-displacement curve of an uncoated bundle loaded in static test until complete failure is shown in Fig. 4. The initial non-linear response of the bundle is related to misalignment of the fibers. The initial non-linear response is followed by a linear response of the bundle, where all the fibers have aligned with the direction of the applied tensile load.

From the load-displacement curves, a maximum working load level for fatigue tests was determined as 500N. Below this load level applied in a static test, no apparent fibre breaks were found in most specimens.

Figure 4: Load-displacement curve for uncoated bundle loaded up to complete failure

3.2 Elastic modulus of carbon fibre bundles

As this study is focused on the feasibility of using coated carbon fibres in mechanically demanding applications, an important issue is whether the coating procedure affects the carbon fibre properties. This was done through stiffness determination of fibre bundles with and without coating from static tests and from the static load cycles prior to fatigue cycles (Fig. 3). The effect of coating procedure on the elastic modulus of fibre bundles, E_b , is summarized in Table 1.

Coating type	E_b [GPa]
<i>No coating</i>	172.0
<i>Stiff polymer coating</i>	115.8
<i>Soft polymer coating</i>	106.6

Table 1: Initial elastic modulus of carbon fiber bundles.

The results of elastic modulus in Table 1 are the average of 2 samples tested for each configuration. It is notable from data presented in Table 1 that the coating procedure significantly decreases the initial elastic modulus of the bundles. The initial modulus of bundles coated with soft polymer coating is slightly lower than for bundles with stiff polymer coating. From SEM inspection of coated and uncoated bundles it was noticed that the coated bundles have significantly larger fibre misalignment with respect to the axial direction of the sample compared to uncoated fibre bundles. Occasional fiber breaks were also noticed for the coated bundles meaning that the coating process at present does affect the stiffness of the carbon fibre bundle.

The stiffness of the bundles was calculated taking into account only the fiber total cross-section area and ignoring the presence of polymer coating. However, the stiffness of the polymer coating is extremely low compared to the stiffness of the carbon fibre – the bulk stiffnesses for the polymers studied here are for the soft and stiff polymer <1 MPa and 320 MPa, respectively.

3.3 Mechanical durability of the polymer coating

Based on the determined maximum load (see Fig. 4), mechanical fatigue load cycles were designed for tension-tension fatigue tests of the coated bundles with the aim of applying possibly high loads to study the mechanical durability of different polymer coatings. Two different fatigue load cycles were used in this study with maximum load equal to 400N and 500 N. Since the load ratio in fatigue tests was in all cases equal to $R=0.1$, the minimum load levels in fatigue cycles were 40N and 50N respectively.

Fatigue tests were first performed on samples with stiff coating (60:40 mono:di ratio) using the maximum load in fatigue equal to 400N. A total of 20,000 load cycles were applied on samples and the qualitative inspection of coated bundles in XHR SEM indicated no presence of micro-damage. Then testing of samples with stiff coating was continued for another 50,000 cycles and inspected with SEM after again finding no evidence of micro-damage being present in the polymer coating as a result of mechanical fatigue loading.

Since no damage was found in the stiff coating loaded with 400N maximum load in a load cycle, the maximum load level for samples with soft polymer (100:0 mono:di ratio) was increased to 500N, expecting that due to much lower stiffness of the soft polymer coating, formation of micro-damage at 400 N will be hindered and unlikely.

The effect of cycling mechanical load on the polymeric coating is crucial if the technique is to be used in structural batteries, where an intact coating is the only barrier preventing short-circuits in the final battery. However, damages in the coating due to mechanical forces are not trivial to investigate. The method chosen was an investigation by electron microscopy so to find cracks in the polymeric material leaving bare carbon surfaces. To receive the highest chance to find potential cracks, a thick coating formulation was chosen.

Neither in the soft (fig. 5b) nor in the stiff (fig. 5c) coating any cracks were found in polymer after up to 70,000 cycles of the dynamic fatigue test. As compared to an untreated fibre (fig. 5a), it is clearly visible that a thick and uniform polymeric layer is covering the carbon fibres and that none of the raw carbon surface is visible. This is very promising for the future application of coated fibres in structural batteries, as the polymeric coating must stay intact even after many cycles of high mechanical load. An earlier study on bulk polymer samples, made from monomer A and monomer B, showed that the strain at failures were found in the range 20-40 % for monomer A:monomer ratios of 30:70 to 70:30. It is therefore not completely unexpected to find that the polymer coatings could cope with the mechanical forces, but as it is crucial to the battery function that the coatings are left without pin-holes or cracks after fatigue it is important to determine this experimentally.

Figure 5: SEM images for (a) Untreated fibre (b) Soft coating 100 mm – cyclic fatigue test (c) Stiff coating – 100 mm – cyclic fatigue test

To further examine the effect of high mechanical loads on the fibre coatings, samples with the stiffer polymer subjected to static loading to complete bundle failure were examined with SEM (fig. 6). As in the case with the dynamic loading no cracks were found on the polymer coating.

Figure 6: SEM images for the static tests on stiff coating (30 mm bundle length). a) and b) are from the same sample using different magnifications.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A feasibility study of polymer coated carbon fibres for use in structural batteries has been performed. The coated fibres were subjected to cyclic mechanical load up to approximately 1 % strain for up to 70,000 cycles. The fibre bundles themselves were seen to experience some losses in stiffness over cycling and the fibre coating process appeared to have an influence on the bundle stiffness, most likely due to fibre breakage or misalignment.

The polymer coating itself was, however, not visibly affected by the prolonged mechanical fatigue. No cracks were observed in the polymeric material which makes the technique promising for future attempts in making truly structural batteries.

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